

Modular Testing Framework for AI Integration in a Spacecraft System: A Case Study from the RAPTOR Project

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Developing and integrating an AI component within critical onboard software developed by a separate entity presents significant challenges, especially when Intellectual Property (IP) constraints limit code sharing [1] [2] [3]. Additionally, the differing technological backgrounds, frameworks, and test requirements of the collaborating entities can make it challenging to share developed components and test scenarios.

At Institute of Research and Technology Saint-Exupery (IRT), the RAPTOR project, in partnership with Thales Alenia Space, encountered these challenges while developing an AI-based image-processing component intended for integration into a Guidance, Navigation, and Control (GNC) closed loop system for space rendezvous.

This paper outlines the solutions implemented in the project. It includes the utilization of a software simulator, the development of a Processor In the Loop (PIL) bench and processes that facilitate component exchanges between the two test environments while safeguarding IP. By employing a modular test bench, high-fidelity experiments have been conducted and software versions of developed AI-based image processing have been integrated into the software simulator. This approach demonstrates a viable way of doing for software projects aiming to integrate AI components developed by separate entities, ensuring efficient integration and testing processes while guarantying IP integrity.

1 Introduction

Developing efficient AI models for space-graded hardware targets often necessitates the collaboration between teams coming from different entities, such as an onboard software integration team with specific domain expertise from industry, and an AI compo-

nent development team from a research laboratory or another industrial actor. However, such a collaboration can be complicated by the use of different domain-specific tools and validation methods. Additionally, key components may be covered by Intellectual Property (IP) right, posing significant challenges during the AI-based components integration process. Furthermore, AI components necessitate performance analysis tests to identify their domain of optimal behavior.

To address these challenges, there is a need for an exchange mechanism between each team test environments to facilitate component validation, delivery and integration. Furthermore, to accommodate the iterative nature of component development, a modular approach is beneficial. Such an approach enables the execution of consistent test scenarios across multiple component versions. Managing IP constraints may require ensuring component integration through well-defined shared interfaces and exchanging these components as "black boxes" implementing or utilizing these interfaces.

RAPTOR is a project led at the French Institute of Research and Technology Saint-Exupery (IRT), aiming to evaluate the use of AI for satellite vision-based navigation for space rendezvous. Specifically, it focuses on the implementation and evaluation of promising AI-based image processing solutions for satellite pose estimation. Thales Alenia Space as satellite prime integrator, partner and co-founder of RAPTOR, provides external components that are key elements for the project. They include a high fidelity image generator, a Dynamic Kinetic and Environment (DKE) simulator, and a Guidance, Navigation, and Control (GNC) onboard software [4]. The main goal is to develop several versions of AI-based image processing and to integrate them into the GNC closed loop, using all the above listed components, in order to characterize their impact on GNC sub-system performances.

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On one hand, the external components contain proprietary information. They can only be shared as black box components, with a given interface and some configuration properties. On the other hand, RAPTOR AI-based image processing solutions can be used without obfuscation within the project.

On the AI Component Developer side (see Figure 1), training and validation losses have been monitored to prevent overfitting. Then, an initial test environment has been set up to carry out an initial performance analysis in Python on the test dataset (orientation and position error as a function of distance, outliers, etc.). On the System Integrator side, the external software test environment embeds software components (GNC and DKE) developed and run using MATLAB[®]. AI models have therefore been integrated in this environment. MATLAB[®] data analysis tools have been used to monitor test results.

Hardware deployment tests at GNC and image processing level must be realized to ensure proper behaviour in performances and latency of algorithms when implemented on board. For image processing, the test system needs to be compatible with several targets. Therefore, the Processor In the Loop (PIL) vision bench requires a high-fidelity bench with all the components in closed-loop and some specific hardware target involved, while remaining simple to set up and to use.

Presenting a methodology tested on a typical use case, this paper aims to prove the benefit of collaborating in space industry with AI component development entities. The main concepts of testing sharing can be transferable to similar projects.

2 Results

This section firstly presents the global development and delivery workflow followed by the project. Then the main test environments are detailed.

2.1 Global Delivery Workflow Overview

Figure 1 presents the development and delivery workflow followed in the RAPTOR project. An AI vision-based pose estimation solution has been developed by the project. The AI training, validation and testing process uses the PyTorch framework and a dedicated dataset composed of synthetic images produced as part of the RAPTOR project using SPICaM (Spacecraft and Planetary Imaging by Camera Modeling), a high fidelity camera model developed by Thales Alenia Space[5]. This realistic dataset has been carefully developed and tuned to ensure the coverage of all op-

Figure 1: AI component and system integration development and test environments, and delivery workflow between them.

erational situations as well as quantification of algorithm robustness and performances.

The image processing model is then delivered to the system integrator in charge of the development of the the Guidance Navigation And Control (GNC) to be integrated as a smart sensor model in the Model In the Loop (MIL) simulator. This step allows to assess the proper behavior of the full vision-based navigation control loop. It also allows to compare to PIL closed-loop results by running the same scenarios to check consistency between both test environments.

The AI deployment on target is done in parallel. Deliveries were deployed on a Jetson AGX Orin, using the TensorRT optimization and runtime framework. To perform this deployment, the AI model is converted to Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX) format, before being imported, optimized and used by TensorRT. This step gives some insight into the inference time and the accuracy in an embedded target.

Finally, compiled external components from system integrator and on-target image processing developed in previous steps are integrated on the PIL bench, on AI development team side. This bench allows to develop and validate image processing to on-board processor interfaces while ensuring proper real time behavior.

2.2 Navigation Performance Validation

The AI-based model trained on a large dataset requires careful validation to assess its performance and to define its operational domain. Performance are statistically validated over the synthetic dataset that must be as close as possible to the operational domain considering key physical and mission properties. This

methodology has been described in [5]. Nevertheless, to assess the domain shift, the acquisition of a set of Hardware-In-the-Loop (HIL) data consisting of representative sequences using a robotic arm, a camera and a mock-up satellite is also investigated.

The SPICaM image simulator is based on a physical ray tracing engine and allows full control over 3D model optical properties, optical sensor parameters, and in-flight geometrical scenarios.

To ensure generalization of the algorithm, the test dataset is produced by the system integrator and split into 2 domains. A nominal test domain providing the nominal algorithm performances and a disturbed test domain that represents worst-case conditions that would be encountered in flight.

This procedure can be used to measure an initial level of domain gap robustness on synthetic images.

Specific metrics have also been developed to monitor performance with respect to distance to the target and to identify outliers. These metrics are based on robust Gaussian model fit specifically developed for the pose estimation task. Identification of outliers is used to better understand the operational domain of the algorithm.

In addition to tests on the image database, temporal scenarios are generated as a Monte Carlo campaign to validate navigation performances including the AI model and a Kalman filter. These scenarios enable a thorough validation of AI in the navigation filter interface and fine performance validation.

2.3 Software Simulator

Figure 2: Software simulator components and runtime data flow.

The software simulator intends to help GNC team

to develop, test and assess the performances of the GNC subsystem, including the AI-based pose estimation function. Figure 2 presents its global architecture.

Test scenarios, DKE and GNC components are developed in a MATLAB® environment. SPICaM and image processing are run as separate processes, connected by specific well-defined interfaces built on TCP links. With this architecture, test scenarios can be prepared, run and analysed directly in the system integrator environment.

Having an hardware independent simulator makes it easier to instantiate it several times. This can facilitate the teamwork, and make it possible to run many simulations in batches, to perform Monte-Carlo simulations.

The presented software simulator is a flexible and scalable approach that still offering a sufficient level of fidelity to evaluate image processing robustness and reliability under any desired conditions. Interfacing it well in MATLAB® environment avoids any additional work for GNC, DKE and scenario integration. Using TCP interfaces offers modularity, keeping SPICaM and AI solution as external components. Updating their versions is made simple, without requiring any new integration work.

Compiled components implementing these TCP interfaces can be delivered to AI development team. SPICaM is delivered compiled. GNC system is autocoded in C by MATLAB® and delivered compiled for an ARM target. DKE is autocoded in C by MATLAB® and delivered as a compiled library. Scenarios are compiled and delivered as executable binaries with a dependence on DKE library.

2.4 Processor-In-the-Loop (PIL) Bench

Given defined scenarios, the PIL bench aims to evaluate performances and latencies of different versions of on-target AI-based image processing running in a high fidelity GNC closed loop system. As illustrated in Figure 3, the PIL bench is separated in four processes: SPICaM, image processing, GNC, and DKE (this last, including scenarios). These processes communicate with each other by the defined messages on TCP links. This brings the modularity required to evaluate several runtimes and hardware targets in a GNC closed loop.

For the moment, for AI-based pose estimation in the PIL bench, a Jetson AGX Orin target is used. Previous generations of the NVIDIA Jetson family of embedded GPU have been tested under radiation or already flew on a cubesat [6] [7]. In addition, this GPU has the capability to emulate other boards of the Jetson family, increasing the modularity of this bench. For the

Figure 3: PIL bench components and runtime data flow.

need of RAPTOR project, this bench shall be able to evaluate the deployment on other targets, for instance space qualified System on Chip (SoC) [8].

The GNC system components are deployed on a ZedBoard, a development board based on Zynq7000 architecture, including an ARM Cortex-A9 processor [9]. This gives us the possibility to collect approximate measurements of latency for this component.

SPICaM, DKE and scenarios are delivered compiled and ready to run on PIL bench server.

2.5 Components and Results Versioning

One drawback of the flexibility offered by the presented solution is that every result requires a complete component version traceability to be exploited or compared to one another. It shall be possible to trace precisely the versions of the components that were used, and for each received component, the details of what was used to generate it. Some components are used at multiple places in the workflow illustrated in (Figure 1). It may be particularly important to keep some global version consistency for a given component.

3 Discussion

This section explores potential enhancements of the presented methodology and discusses how these solutions could be adapted for similar applications.

3.1 AI Software Runtime with Intellectual Property

In the RAPTOR case, there was no need to protect AI deliveries. This permits a direct delivery of Py-

Torch inference scripts. However, in different contexts, sharing the source code of an AI inference software may not be feasible. In this last case, the delivery flow could be adapted to the use of an alternative framework runtime like ONNX Runtime, delivering image processing as a compiled binary. Compiled TensorRT code could also be used. But as its compilation is specific to the execution environment, it would require an anticipated choice of hardware from all the partners.

3.2 Multiple AI Components and Partners

The proposed solution could be adapted for the integration of multiple AI components from various external partners into a unique GNC closed loop system or other onboard subsystems. This scalability allows for broader applications of more complex projects, demonstrating the adaptability of the solution for different types of AI components and embedded systems.

3.3 SoC Target Integration

In addition to the NVIDIA Jetson AGX Orin GPU, work is carried on deploying image processing on the Advanced Micro Devices (AMD) Ultrascale+ ZCU104 target, a System on Chip (SoC) board that includes an FPGA component. Once the model has been trained and validated, the selected candidate goes through the board optimization and deployment chain. In the case of the ZCU104, the Vitis AI [10] chain enables an initial optimisation stage to be carried out using the Vitis AI Optimizer tool, followed by a quantization stage using Vitis AI Quantizer. Finally, the model is compiled (Vitis AI Compiler), deployed on the target and on-board inference is performed using the Runtime library (Vitis AI Runtime). Following the established delivery workflow of Figure 1, this new target will be integrated into the PIL bench after completing the "Target deployment" step. This integration will allow to compare different target types and access models from the VitisAI Model Zoo, for quick evaluation and experimentation on existing model architectures.

3.4 Target Choice Guidelines

Going from one target to another have been more complicated than expected in our case. Some good lesson learnt might be firstly to choose an hardware target early. Secondly to deploy a first simple version of the model as early as possible, checking its portability early and dealing with hardware deployment issues before the model gets to complicated. And thirdly to

iterate with small step from there, following an agile type of approach. These guidelines are compatible with the proposed workflow and would have helped us save some precious time and avoid being stuck for a long time on complex and tool chain specific technical problems. Looking at several target for this project and deploying on two of them, using very different tool chains made us realized how much the hardware target choice and deployment methods available can impact deployment time. This may also be taken into account when choosing an hardware target. For instance, in our case : a CPU target deployment using ONNX runtime seems quicker than porting on GPU target using TensorRT, that is quicker than porting on a SoC compatible with Vitis AI, that seems far quicker than porting on an FPGA without Vitis AI compatibility.

3.5 Hardware Optimized Model Delivery

Target optimizations, such as quantization, can slightly affect model outputs. After the target deployment phase, measured data such as inference time in addition with a software version of the optimized model could be provided to the system integrator to enhance the precision of the software simulator. This process is represented by the dotted arrow labeled "metadata and optimized model" in Figure 1.

4 Conclusion

The RAPTOR study case demonstrated a successful approach when system integration and AI development external teams are involved in different project environments. The approach permits in particular to develop AI-based components separately and to integrate them into an onboard critical loop while respecting intellectual property constraints. By sharing the methodology and results of the presented specific use case, this paper aims to foster collaboration in the space industry between external entities, about AI component development, sharing, and testing. The main concepts presented can be transferred to similar projects, promoting the adoption of good practices.

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